

CURRENT METHODS OF TEACHING L2 FOR DIFFERENT AGE OF PUPILS

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Annotation: In the last few decades, education has begun to make more space for diverse learners — students with special needs, learning disabilities or even different learning styles. There’s still a long way to go when it comes to making our classrooms open and equitable, but many modern teaching methods are highly adaptable and address some of the issues diverse learners have in a traditional classroom. Ultimately, there’s no “best way” to teach, regardless of what kind of students you have in your class. There are, however, some general guidelines you can follow to make sure your instruction is as effective as possible

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Today’s teachers face lots of challenges and have lots of opportunities: The shift to remote learning exposed inequality in classrooms, but also offered new ways for students to engage with interactive learning experiences. New edtech innovations connect classroom learning with real-world digital skills. Changing ideas about education and pedagogy have added new learning objectives like social-emotional learning, differentiation and personalized learning. Don’t be afraid to try new ways for students to learn and stay engaged. Keep reading to find out which teaching style works best for your classroom!

A teacher uses new teaching methods with a student at the whiteboard in english class.

1. Direct Instruction

Best for: All ages, when combined with other teaching methods. Direct instruction is when you explicitly convey concepts and skills to students, rather than letting them learn on their own. While it might seem odd to start off a list of modern teaching methods with a technique that’s been the foundation of traditional classroom instruction for hundreds of years, direct instruction allows

you to layer on more recent teaching strategies. When combined with other teaching strategies, direct instruction is a useful tool for boosting student comprehension! Today, it can include anything from lectures and educational videos to tutorials and workshops.

Example:

Students attend a classroom lecture about ecological diversity, then watch a video from a local conservation group about efforts to preserve local habitats. This direct instruction helps you explain the requirements of a service learning project they're doing to clean up the park near their school.

2. Flipped classrooms

Three young female students participate in a flipped classroom activity. Best for: Late elementary and up, or any students who can work independently. Homework at home, lectures at school — that's how it's usually done. But in flipped classrooms, students absorb information on their own time, and use in-class time for hands-on learning and problem solving. Also known as blended learning, flipped classrooms embrace new edtech innovations and prioritize face-to-face learning activities in order to boost student engagement. It helps students move at their own pace and gives you more time to provide one-on-one support where needed. When combined with techniques like experiential learning or inquiry-based learning, flipped classrooms can give students valuable hands-on experience.

Example:

Students read an article about a specific scientific procedure at home, then come to class and do a hands-on experiment. They write up their findings and give a presentation about their results. While they work, you observe student work to spot learning gaps you can address in future lessons.

3. Kinesthetic learning

Best for: All ages. Kinesthetic learning is a specific learning style also known as tactile learning. Kinesthetic learners absorb information best when it's presented through hands-on demonstrations, active learning and manipulatives. Kinesthetic learning is a great modern teaching method for all learners because it gives students more ways to explore concepts and get hands-on, real-life experiences in their learning environment that translate to better learning outcomes.

Example:

Students learning how to do multiplication participate in a variety of station rotation activities, including: Answering multiplication questions in Prodigy

Math Game Working with base ten blocks and other math manipulatives
Working in small groups with the teacher to address learning gaps

4. Game-based learning

A student uses a tablet for game-based learning. Best for: All ages, depending on the game. Game-based learning (GBL) is a modern teaching method that uses the power of games to define and support learning outcomes. Game-based learning actually uses games to teach, as opposed to gamification, which uses game elements like leaderboards and points to motivate learning. Educational games promote engagement, provide immediate rewards and feedback, and harness the power of healthy competition to keep kids excited to learn. Today's students understand games, especially digital games, intimately. Edtech tools can help turn their love for video games into a love of learning, whether they're at school or at home.

Example:

Prodigy Math Game is a game-based learning platform designed to help students love practicing math skills. Plus, free teacher tools mean you can align Prodigy to whatever you're teaching in the classroom in just a few easy steps. Set up a Plan for curriculum-aligned math practice on a new concept, or send students an Assignment to differentiate and assess learning progress. Screenshot of a question in Prodigy Math Game, a game-based learning platform. Students won't know they're being assessed or doing homework — it's all part of the adventure! Sign up for your free teacher account today to get started.

5. Student-centered learning

Best for: All ages. Above all, student-centered learning involves students in decisions about their learning. It connects student interest to the classroom and builds an assessment framework to help them understand why the material is important and how it fits into everyday life. For better or worse, the internet has opened up new ways for students to receive information and engage with the world. Student-centered learning helps: Give them the tools they need to engage with new topics. Make connections between topics and boost problem-solving skills. Directly relate classroom lessons with what they're experiencing outside of school

Example:

Interdisciplinary learning is a great way to tie student interests to your curriculum. Students can read a novel about a specific scientific discovery and submit a book report, or create a budget for marketing a made-up product in

math class. Work with students to find out what they like, how they learn best and how the project will be assessed.

6. Teacher-centered learning

Students learn using a teacher-centered teaching method. Best for: Elementary and up — younger students may need more hands-on interaction to stay focused . Teacher-centered learning is most similar to traditional classroom learning. Students learn mostly independently through lectures and receive clear instructions and rubrics from a central authority figure. Much like direct instruction, teacher-centered learning is useful to provide a foundation for other work. Most modern classrooms prioritize collaboration, group work and student exploration, for good reasons. But independent learning can reach different learning styles and give students a sense of personal accomplishment and accountability!

Example:

Teacher-centered learning can still be engaging and motivating for students. If you're starting a new novel study or ELA unit, why not have students journal independently about what they think will happen in the story or what questions they have about the concept? They'll practice their writing skills, and you can all come back at the end of the unit to see whose predictions were the most accurate.

References:

Ellis, Ryann K. (2009), Field Guide to Education Management, archived from ASTD Learning Circuits, originally dated August 24, 2014, July 5, 2012

Parr, Judy M .; Fung, Irene (October 3, 2006). "A review of the literature on computer-assisted learning, particularly on integrated learning systems and results on literacy and numbers

" New Zealand Ministry of Education. Archived from the original on March 9, 2007. Retrieved 13 February 2013.

